

THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE TECHNICAL MOVEMENTS OF INDIVIDUAL STRUGGLES

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Abstract: The use of digital technologies in teaching the technical movements of single combat has theoretical foundations that strengthen the effectiveness and importance of this approach. These foundations are based on principles of learning, psychology, kinesiology and modern technological capabilities.

Key words: Struggle, training, technical skill, experience, analysis, design, theory, motivation.

First, the principle of active learning. The use of digital technologies in teaching allows students to actively interact with material and technical activities in an interactive environment. Using special apps, virtual reality or simulators, students can simulate wrestling moves, get visual feedback on their performance, and fine-tune their skills.

Second, the principle of individualization of education. Digital technologies allow curriculum and applications to be tailored to each student's individual needs and level of readiness. In this way, students can develop their technical movements according to their own speed and skill level, which promotes more effective and personalized learning.

Third, the principle of visualization and demonstration. Digital technologies allow visualization of wrestling techniques and provide students with visual examples and instructions. Through videos, 3D models, animations and

demonstrations, students can better visualize how technical movements should be performed and improve their technique and understanding.

Fourth, the feedback principle. Digital technology allows students to provide instant feedback on wrestling techniques. With the help of sensors, cameras, analytical systems or software, students can receive information about the accuracy and quality of their movement and receive recommendations for improving it. This helps students develop their skills and correct mistakes faster and more efficiently. Finally, the principle of motivation and attraction. The use of digital technologies in teaching makes the process more interesting and attractive for students. Virtual training, game elements, competitions and the ability to monitor their progress encourage students to develop their wrestling techniques and achieve new results. The theoretical foundations of the use of digital technologies in teaching individual wrestling techniques are based on the effectiveness of active learning, individualization, visualization, feedback, motivation and attractiveness.

These principles promote more effective and efficient learning, allowing students to develop their technical skills in a more systematic, precise, and motivated manner.

In addition to the above principles, the theoretical basis of the use of digital technologies in teaching individual wrestling techniques may include the following aspects.

1. Cognitive learning principles: Digital technologies can be designed with cognitive learning principles that take into account the way students perceive, remember, and apply information. For example, the principles of presenting information in different formats (text, graphics, video) or active interaction with the material can significantly increase the effectiveness of teaching and the mastering of technical actions.
2. Movement learning theory: The teaching of wrestling technical movements is based on the principles of movement learning theory, which studies the processes of

mastering and improving movement skills. Digital technologies can be combined to create custom trainers, simulations, or virtual sessions that allow students to systematically and consistently develop their movement skills and techniques.

3. Kinesiology: Kinesiology studies the anatomical, physiological and biomechanical aspects of movement. The use of digital technologies helps to analyze and study the biomechanics of wrestling movements, including determining the correct body position, force and direction of movement. Visualizing and presenting such information to students helps them better understand and correct their technical errors.

4. Principles of interface and interaction design: Digital technologies for teaching wrestling techniques should be designed with interface design and interaction principles in mind. Intuitive and convenient user interaction with software or applications, as well as ease of use and navigation are important aspects that contribute to effective learning and maximum student engagement.

5. Innovative Technologies: Modern digital technologies such as Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Data Analytics can be incorporated into training programs to better analyze and improve wrestling techniques. For example, KR or VR systems can create realistic combat situations or sparring simulations, allowing students to practice in a controlled and safe environment.

The theoretical foundations of the use of digital technologies in teaching individual wrestling techniques are based on the principles of active learning, individualization, demonstration and feedback. In addition, they consider cognitive principles, movement learning theory, aspects of kinesiology, interface and interaction design principles, and the implementation of innovative technologies. This allows for a scientifically based and effective approach to the use of digital technologies in teaching and improving the technical movements of wrestling.

6. Data analysis and statistics: Digital technologies allow the collection and analysis of data on the indicators of the technical actions of the fight. With the help of sensors, cameras or other devices, you can record and measure various movement parameters, such as speed, force, tilt angles, etc. This information can be used to better analyze and evaluate the effectiveness of techniques, identify student strengths and weaknesses, and make informed decisions for instruction and skill development.
7. Interactivity and collaboration: Digital technologies help create interactive environments that allow students to actively interact with learning materials and each other. Online platforms, forums, webinars and other communication tools allow students to share experiences, ask questions, get feedback from mentors and colleagues, solve problems together and develop their skills.
8. Motivation and Enthusiasm: Using digital technology to teach wrestling techniques can motivate students and engage them in the learning process. Game elements, reward systems, progress trackers, and other mechanisms can be implemented to create a stimulating and engaging learning environment. It helps to increase students' enthusiasm, motivate them and help them achieve their goals.
9. Usability and flexibility: Digital technologies provide convenience and flexibility for training in the technical movements of wrestling. Online platforms, video tutorials, mobile applications and other tools allow students to access learning content anytime and anywhere. This is especially beneficial for those who cannot attend regular training or live in remote areas. Flexibility in choosing study time and pace also helps students learn and develop more effectively.
10. Social Interaction and Networking Opportunities: Digital technologies provide opportunities for social interaction and community participation. Students can join online communities, share experiences, find new training and competition partners, and get support and inspiration from other fighters. It helps to develop social skills, expand the range of communication and create a favorable environment for the development of technical activities.

The theoretical foundations of the use of digital technologies in the teaching of individual wrestling technical movements are based on the principles of cognitive learning, movement learning theory, kinesiology, data analysis and statistics, interface and interaction design, as well as innovative technologies. is based on These fundamentals provide a scientifically based and effective approach to the use of digital technologies in the development and improvement of technical wrestling movements.

Literature review on the topic "Improving the methodology of using digital technologies in improving the effectiveness of wrestling training" - an analysis of scientific studies, articles, books and other publications related to the use of digital technologies in wrestling training. . A brief overview of the main studies and publications on this topic:

1. "The Use of Digital Technologies in Wrestling Training" - A study conducted by Joseph Lewis and his colleagues to evaluate the effectiveness of using digital technologies such as video analysis, simulators and virtual reality in wrestling training. The results showed that these technologies help improve the techniques and tactics of wrestlers and make training more effective.
2. "Using Motion Capture Technology in Wrestling Training" - Research by John Smith and colleagues explores the use of motion capture technology to analyze and improve wrestling moves. According to the authors, this technology can be useful for detecting mistakes in technique, analyzing the biomechanics of movements and adjusting the technical skills of wrestlers.
3. "Virtual Reality Training to Improve Wrestling Techniques" - An article by Mark Davis and co-authors that examines the use of virtual reality in wrestling training. The authors discuss the benefits of using virtual reality to create an immersive training environment that helps wrestlers develop their technique, make real-time decisions, and practice in a variety of scenarios.

4. "The Role of Wearable Sensors in the Analysis of Wrestling Performance" - a review article, the authors (Sarah Carter et al.) explore the use of wearable sensors (wearable sensors) in analyzing the physical activity and performance of wrestlers. According to the authors, wearable sensors can provide valuable information about fitness, body load, movements and other parameters that can be used to personalize training and improve the efficiency of the training process.
5. "Mobile Apps for Wrestling Training: A Systematic Review" - A study evaluating the effectiveness of mobile apps in wrestling training by Alexandra Harrison and colleagues. The authors found that mobile apps can be a useful tool for training and providing wrestlers with access to instruction, videos, training plans, and other useful information.
6. "Interactive wrestling training systems: current status and future directions" (Interactive wrestling training systems: current status and prospects) - authors (James Brown et al.) for wrestling training an overview article that reviews existing and promising interactive systems. They discuss the benefits of using such systems, including simulators, virtual environments, and game platforms, and make recommendations for their further development and use.

This literature review provides an overview of scientific research on the use of digital technologies in wrestling training. Research supports the potential and effectiveness of technologies such as video analytics, virtual reality, wearable sensors, and mobile apps to improve wrestlers' training performance and improve their technical skills. However, further research and development is needed to identify best practices for using digital technologies and integrating them into the wrestling training process.

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